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WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION: IS THERE A RELATION?¹

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ABSTRACT. *Recent literature repeatedly suggests that in the context of sustainable consumer behaviour the workplace has an important role. The workplace can influence consumer behaviour by providing knowledge and creating habits that stimulate sustainable consumption at home. According to existing research, it is a big probability that experience acquired at the workplace will be transferred and used in*

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Human Factor Analysis in the Labour, Economic and Political Environment

private life. On the other hand, the working life determines a number of constraints for sustainable consumption as well. This paper examines the relationship between work-life balance and sustainable consumption in private life among university employees. Although the empirical results allow confirming the positive link, the relation is rather weak, opening the horizons for further exploration of other possible work-related determinants of sustainable consumption.

KEYWORDS: work-life balance, work-life conflict, sustainable consumption, university employees.

JEL classification : E20, I20, M12.

Introduction

Sustainable consumption is a complex and divergent area of scientific research, which unites knowledge of different academic disciplines and creates presumptions for their substantiated transfer to sustainable consumption policy and practice.

Recent literature involves a discussion about the companies' role in promoting sustainable consumption of their employees. The argument behind is that the workplace can influence consumer behaviour by providing knowledge about environmentally friendly, ecological products and creating habits and norms that stimulate sustainable consumption at home. This approach emphasises the workplace as a learning setting, where employees can adopt sustainable behaviour and transfer it into private life. Employees are an important target group for internal CSR activities of companies, concerning health and safety actions, labour rights, learning/training or work-life balance arrangements (Muster, 2011). However, companies usually do not really care about private sustainable consumption of their employees; they do not recognize employees as consumers nor the effects the organisation can have on employees' private consumption behaviour in general. Among research about companies' role in promoting sustainable consumption, there are a number of studies examining the negative impact of work-life on sustainable consumption behaviour in private life (Schor, 2005; Devetter, Rousseau, 2011; Muster, 2012). Usually, those studies involve such work interferences as working time, working conditions, separation of work and home, job stress, work-life conflicts, negative spill-overs or compensation effects. It is nevertheless true that evidence base linking workplace to sustainable consumption in private life remains conceptually and empirically underdeveloped.

Muster, Schrader (2011) proposed the idea of "Green Work-Life Balance" as a concept for promoting sustainable consumption, but mostly their assumptions that work-life balance can lead to more sustainable consumption in private life were based on qualitative research results or reflected only conceptual considerations. Therefore, this study *aims* to further extend knowledge of the relation between working life and sustainable consumption. More specifically, we aim to reveal the theoretically assumed relation between work-life balance and sustainable consumption in private life in a sample of university employees.

1. Theoretical background

1.1. Sustainable Consumption

The richness and variety of scientific research in the area of sustainable consumption (SC) shows undeniable importance and relevance of the topic. However, there is still no consensus regarding the definition of SC. According to Mont, Plepys (2008), the notion of sustainable consumption is often used as an umbrella term for issues related to human needs, equity, quality of life, resource efficiency, waste minimization, life cycle thinking, consumer health and safety, consumer sovereignty, etc. Sustainable consumption represents “the demand-side of the consumption/production sustainability coin” (Bentley, De Leeuw, 2009, p.354), therefore it should be distinguished from broader issues of sustainable development. Some research talks about sustainable consumption as a production issue, others relate to the green market, still, others speak about the reduction of consumption. Anyway, everybody agrees that SC calls for potential changes in consumer behaviour, including efficient consumption of goods and services, using fewer resources, reusing and recycling, sharing, etc.

The scientific literature reveals three broad areas in which sustainable consumption manifests – economic, social and environmental (Balderjahn, *et al.*, 2013; Phipps, *et al.*, 2013). However, existing empirical research usually involves one of those areas within a particular industry sector. Marketing and consumer behaviour research in the context of SC usually deals with ecological/environmental issues (Young, *et al.*, 2010; Leary, *et al.*, 2014; Spaargaren, 2003) analysing consumer attitudes, values, beliefs, norms and behaviour towards buying products that are a bit more sustainable or “green”, disposition of waste and other related activities. The social dimension of sustainable consumption usually relates to behaviour that intends to help or provide benefit for other individuals or groups. Therefore, the research on social dimension usually focuses on consumer attitudes to fair trade and social responsibility of companies (Castaldo, *et al.*, 2009; Connolly, Shaw, 2006). Economic dimension usually is related to financial profitability of companies, but in the context of SC, it is defined as conscious care for long-term economic and personal welfare (Balderjahn, *et al.*, 2013; Sheth, *et al.*, 2011) and involves decisions whether to acquire some products or not. Increasing awareness about environmental and social issues leads to an understanding that overconsumption can occur even with green products.

Taking the view that sustainable consumption is multi-dimensional in nature and varying approaches might be taken to investigate such behaviour, four different types of it (eco-conscious buying, healthy lifestyle, resource efficiency, and post-consumption) were distinguished in the present study. The rationale for distinguishing those four types lays in works of Leary *et al.* (2014) and Chen (2009). Eco-conscious buying in our research was defined as the willingness of consumers to select and purchase products that are less harmful to the environment, labelled as ecological or locally produced. Resource efficiency behaviour reflected the conscious use of electricity, water and transportation. Post-consumption behaviour involved responsible disposal of products through recycling, charity or sharing; and healthy lifestyle was defined as daily habits considering food and drinks. Those four types intended to capture not only different stages of sustainable consumption (buying, use, disposal) but different aspects (environmental, social and economic) as well.

1.2. Work-Life Balance and Other Work-Related Factors

Sustainable consumption behaviour is a part of daily living and as people spend most of their time at work, the workplace becomes an important setting for learning. According to Muster, “workplace conditions have the power to broaden or constrain the opportunities people have to behave in certain ways, including sustainable consumption behaviour” (Muster, 2011, p.161). Viola Muster in a series of her papers (Muster, 2011, Muster, 2012) developed the idea about “green” work-life balance. The concept of work-life balance (WLB) is widely analysed in psychology, sociology, human resource management and other fields of science. Many of those studies had focused on influences arising from working life and affecting the private life or vice versa (Kinman, Jones, 2008; Muster, 2012; Greenhaus, *et al.*, 2012; Russo *et al.*, 2016). Work-life balance can be defined as an individual’s perception of how well his/ her life roles are balanced (Russo, *et al.*, 2016). In work-life research, the WLB often is analysed through the construct of work-life conflict (WLC), a form of inter-role conflict, which occurs when role demands of one domain (i.e. work) are not compatible with the demands of another domain (i.e. home, family, leisure). Conflicts may take several forms, but those derived from time devoted to work role and strains produced by this role considered to be the most important.

Whilst the work-life conflict might be a possible predictor of sustainable consumption patterns in private life, other variables are also likely to be important. The present study investigates whether specific work-related factors, like working hours and when those hours fall within 24 h, work schedule flexibility and organisational support for work-life balance relate to sustainable consumption in private life. As WLC involves time-based and strain-based conflicts, the above-mentioned factors might be seen as composite parts of WLC. However, several studies in work-life research area indicate those factors as independent variables that can influence the WLC itself (Kinman, Jones, 2008; Russo, *et al.*, 2016). Meanwhile, research on sustainable consumption that focuses on how SC is restrained because of working life usually analyses working time, working conditions, separation of work and home, etc., as independent predictors of less sustainably consumption behaviour (Schor, 2005; Pullinger, 2009).

Based on the existing literature (Muster, 2011; Schor, 2005) the following assumptions have been made:

A1: Work-life conflict will be negatively related to sustainable consumption in private life. High work demands and working pressure are assumed to negatively affect sustainable consumption. Individuals with high work demands often look for consumption options that require the least work and those options are also frequently unsustainable.

A2: Number of working hours and when those hours fall within 24h will be negatively related to sustainable consumption in private life. Working time cuts off available free time and sustainable behaviour is often more time consuming than less sustainable activities.

A3: Flexible work schedule will be positively related to sustainable consumption in private life. Flexible work schedule determines the conduct of everyday life and the allocation of free time; therefore, it may allow constructing one’s own activities in a more sustainable way.

A4: Organisational support for its employee’s work-life balance will be positively related to sustainable consumption in private life. This assumption is based on the general assumption that work-life balance is positively related with sustainable consumption in private life; logically if a company shows support for WLB of its employees, it should reflect positive link with consumption patterns.

Despite the number of conceptual considerations, there is not much empirical evidence about the relationship between work-life conflict or other work-related factors and sustainable consumption. Therefore, the present study serves as an attempt to enrich an empirical base for further discussions.

2. Research Design

2.1 Participants

The higher education sector was chosen for this research as representing setting where life and career situation is a sensitive issue and thus may provide a more robust examination of the relations between work-life balance and sustainable consumption in private life. The current situation in the higher education sector in Lithuania suggests that university employees generally perceive their jobs as having become increasingly more demanding as a result of restructuring and merging, commercialisation, competition, reductions in funding, etc. Kinman, Jones (2008) in their study of employees of the UK universities also highlighted heavy workload and time and resource constraints as the most stressful aspects of academic work (Kinman, Jones, 2008).

Questionnaires were sent to ten universities in Lithuania for academic and academic-related staff. In total, 439 completed questionnaires were returned.

Seventy-two per cent of respondents were female. The age ranged from 23 to 72 years with the mean age of 43 years. The majority of respondents lived with other family members (85 per cent) and had children (69 per cent). 83 per cent of respondents indicated themselves as academic staff, the rest 17 per cent represented non-academic personnel.

2.2 Measures

Sustainable consumption. The prevalent understanding that sustainable behaviour is multi-dimensional in nature led us to use four different sets of SC in our research: eco-conscious buying behaviour (3 items), resource efficiency behaviour (4 items), post-consumption behaviour (4 items), and healthy lifestyle (3 items). Each of four dimensions was measured with three or four items on a 5-point scale (1 – “never” to 5 – “always”). Authors based on previous works (Leary, et al., 2014, Wang, et al., 2014, Chen, 2009, etc) developed the scale. It is important to notice that among numerous research on sustainable consumption there is still a lack of comprehensive measurement scale that would involve several aspects of SC.

Exploratory factor analysis (principal component method with Varimax rotation) resulted in 5 factors (KMO – 0.803, $p < 0.001$) and not four as theoretically assumed. One item from “recourse efficiency behaviour” scale – “I choose the more environment-friendly type of transportation for my route to work (e.g. walking, biking or using public transportation)” – fell into separate factor, which was named “Mobility”. All other factors retained the same structure as theoretically designed. Five factors accounted for 62.258 % of the variability of the original 14 items. Internal consistency of sub-scales and the overall scale was tested and Cronbach’ alpha coefficients showed a sufficient level of reliability (see *Table 1*).

Human Factor Analysis in the Labour, Economic and Political Environment

Table 1. Results of EFA and reliability of SC subscales

Items	Alpha	Factor loadings
Factor 1. Resource efficiency behaviour	0,682	
1. I turn off the lights in rooms at home if I'm not in them at the moment		,779
2. I turn off the computer if I'm not using it for a while		,735
3. I turn off the water tap (e.g. don't let the water run while I brush my teeth)		,692
Factor 2. Eco-conscious buying behaviour	0,671	
1. When I purchase products, I devote time to find out whether they are environment-friendly, made from materials low in pollutants.		,728
2. When I purchase products, I look for products made in my native country.		,750
3. When I purchase food, I look for ecological food products.		,804
Factor 3. Post-consumption behaviour	0,609	
1. I recycle waste at home.		,462
2. I deliver old pharmaceuticals to the drugstores.		,662
3. I deliver batteries of electronic devices to designated areas.		,768
4. I give my old clothing and footwear for people who need it or deliver to designated areas.		,610
Factor 4. Healthy lifestyle	0,630	
1. It happens that I purchase more food than I can consume (r)*.		,768
2. I buy more fast-preparing food on workdays (r).		,621
3. I just want to relax with my favourite drink at hand on workday evenings (r).		,601
Factor 5. Mobility	n.a.	
1. I choose more environment-friendly type of transportation for my route to work (e.g. walking, biking or using public transportation)		,797
The overall scale of Sustainable Consumption	0,713	

Note: * (r) - reverse coded items

Source: based on Leary *et al.*, 2014; Wang *et al.*, 2014; Chen, 2009.

Work-life conflict. A five-item scale adapted from the one developed by Netemeyer, *et al.*, (1996) was used to measure work-life conflict (Netemeyer, *et al.*, 1996). The scale was designed as a one-dimensional measure, although it encompasses aspects of the time-based and strain-based conflict. The items were anchored on a 5-point Likert type scale (1 – “strongly disagree” to 5 – “strongly agree”). Higher mean scores in this scale denote a higher level of work-life conflict and thus the lower level of work-life balance. Exploratory factor analysis confirmed the one-dimensional structure of the scale and the Cronbach’ alpha coefficient (0.912) showed high internal consistency.

Work-related factors included items for measuring work schedule flexibility (“In my work I can have a flexible work schedule (e.g., some works I can do at home”), work hours (“I often work more than 40 hours per week”), working time (“I often have to work till late in the evening, at nights and on weekends”) and organisational support for work-life balance (“My organisation supports its employees striving for work-life balance”). They were developed based on the works of Muster (2012) and Kinman, Jones (2008). All items were anchored on a 5-point Likert type scale (1 – “strongly disagree” to 5 – “strongly agree”).

3. Results

The results showed a relatively high level of WLC, with the mean score of 3.64 (SD - 0.94) (on a 5-point scale) (see *Table 2*). Academic work is essentially demanding, with multiple roles and a number of stressful aspects. Not surprisingly university employees encounter difficulties in maintaining an acceptable work-life balance.

Human Factor Analysis in the Labour, Economic and Political Environment

Table 2. Descriptive analysis of WLC (N= 439)

Items	Mean	SD
1. The demands of my work interfere with my life away from work.	3.58	1.13
2. The amount of time my job takes up makes it difficult to fulfil other interests.	3.66	1.09
3. Things I want to do at home do not get done because of the demands of my job.	3.80	1.07
4. My job produces a strain that makes it difficult to fulfil other responsibilities and duties.	3.61	1.09
5. Due to work, I have to make changes to my plans for activities away from work.	3.56	1.08
The overall scale of WLC	3.64	0.94

Source: own calculations

Significant relationships were observed between WLC and other work-related variables, except for schedule flexibility. Differently from previous empirical findings (Kinman, Jones, 2008), we did not find any relation between flexible work schedule and work-life conflict. WLC was negatively associated with organisational support, ($r = -0.361, p < 0.01$), i.e., stronger support from the employer would allow maintaining better work-life balance for employees. WLC was positively associated with work time ($r = 0.598, p < 0.01$) and work hours ($r = 0.565, p < 0.01$), i.e., respondents who reported longer work hours and frequent work in late evenings or at weekends, reported higher levels of work-life conflict (see *Table 3*).

Table 3. Descriptives and correlations between WLC and other work-related factors

Variable	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
1. Work-Life conflict	3.64	0.94	1.000				
2. Schedule flexibility	3.68	1.11	.049	1.000			
3. Work hours	3.92	1.16	.565**	.106*	1.000		
4. Work time	3.79	1.22	.598**	.210**	.724**	1.000	
5. Organisational support	2.36	1.01	-.361**	.165**	-.254**	-.321**	1.000

Note: ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$ (2-tailed). N – 439.

Source: own calculations

Table 4. Descriptives and correlations between WLC and Sustainable Consumption

Variable	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. Work-life conflict	3.64	0.94	1.000						
2. Resource efficiency	4.03	0.80	-0.051	1.000					
3. Buying	3.26	0.69	-0.03	.192**	1.000				
4. Post-consumption	3.35	0.86	-0.036	.345**	.315**	1.000			
5. Lifestyle	3.25	0.67	-.158**	.137**	.173**	.172**	1.000		
6. Mobility	2.74	1.49	-.100*	.182**	.055	.103*	.016	1.000	
7. Overall SC	3.47	0.48	-.105*	.632**	.569**	.789**	.441**	.340**	1.000

Note: ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$ (2-tailed). N – 439.

Source: own calculations

Significant negative (though weak) relationship was found between WLC and healthy lifestyle, WLC and mobility, and between WLC and overall sustainable consumption (see *Table 4*). The higher level of WLC, the less sustainable diet habits occur. It partly confirms the assumption that employees might attempt to mitigate stressors in the workplace with unsustainable consumption, such as fast food and alcohol drinking. At the same time, it clearly shows that WLC

Human Factor Analysis in the Labour, Economic and Political Environment

does not foster the choice of more sustainable transport alternatives. Although none other relations were significant, all of them were negative in relation to WLC.

Correlation between SC dimensions and work-related factors showed that significant associations occurred between schedule flexibility and eco-conscious buying ($r = -0.099, p < 0.05$) and lifestyle ($r = -0.122, p < 0.05$). In both cases, the relation was negative and very weak. It seems that the flexibility of work schedule, possibility to work at home somehow leads to less sustainable buying and living habits. In general, such findings contradict the prevalent assumption that ability to adapt working hours to meet personal/family needs increase the ability to maintain a better work-life balance. A possible explanation might be the context chosen for the present research – higher education sector – flexible work schedule is quite common for academic employees. It might be that schedule flexibility is more associated with instability, an inconsistency that burdens life planning instead of making it easier. Significant negative relations were also observed between mobility and work hours ($r = -0.111, p < 0.05$) and work time ($r = -0.118, p < 0.05$) (see *Table 5*). Majority of respondents reported long work hours and often working at nights and weekends. Time is very precious when you lack it. Therefore, not many respondents think about a more sustainable choice of transport when going to work, because it would take much more time.

Table 5. Descriptives and correlations between Work-related factors and Sustainable Consumption

	Schedule flexibility	Work hours	Work time	Organisational support
Resource efficiency	-.059	.010	-.022	.006
Buying	-.099*	-.032	-.013	.086
Post-consumption	-.081	-.087	-.021	.012
Lifestyle	-.122*	-.067	-.064	-.012
Mobility	-.041	-.111*	-.118*	.036
Overall SC	-.112*	-.080	-.068	.026

Note: * $p < 0.05$ (2-tailed). N – 439.

Source: own calculations

In order to examine the predictors of sustainable consumption, a multiple regression equation was computed with work-life conflict and other work-related factors as independent variables and overall sustainable consumption as a dependent variable. The results of the regression indicated that WLC and other factors explained only 4% of the variance in overall sustainable consumption ($R^2 = 0.041, F(5, 399) = 3,374, p < 0.01$). Analysis of coefficients showed that only two out of five factors significantly predicted value of sustainable consumption, i.e., schedule flexibility ($\beta = -0.164, p < 0.01$) and work-life conflict ($\beta = -0.128, p < 0.05$). The same multiple regression analyses were performed with the five dimensions of sustainable consumption as dependent variables. The regression model conditionally fitted the requirements for interpretation only in case with lifestyle as a dependent variable. Work-life conflict and other work-related factors explained 5 percent of the variance in healthy lifestyle ($R^2 = 0.046, F(5, 397) = 3,826, p < 0.01$). Again, only work-life conflict and work schedule flexibility had significant negative impact on lifestyle (accordingly $\beta = -0.214, p < 0.01$ and $\beta = -0.119, p < 0.05$). Although the explaining power in regression models was too small for meaningful interpretation, the results could serve as a basis for a better understanding of how working life is related to sustainable behaviour patterns in private life.

Human Factor Analysis in the Labour, Economic and Political Environment

In order to better explore the possible relations between work-life balance and sustainable consumption, new variable “work-life balance” (WLB) was created by transforming WLC into WLB with three levels (good balance/moderate balance/no balance). Transformation of work-life conflict to work-life balance resulted in three levels: only 7.3 per cent of all respondents maintained good balance, 48.4 per cent fell into average balance category, and 44.3 per cent had no work-life balance at all. From the practical point those results are very important as employees with no work-life balance encounter big risk of stress, health problems and burnout that in turn leads to decrease in motivation, productivity, work satisfaction, etc. Kruskal-Wallis H test for independent samples confirmed the significant differences in sustainable consumption based on the WLB level ($Chi-Square = 8.956$, $df (2)$, $p < 0.01$). Analysis of mean ranks clearly indicated that those with good balance tended to demonstrate higher level of sustainable consumption in private life than those with no work-life balance.

As the literature indicates possible differences in work-life balance and sustainable consumption behaviour based on socio-demographic characteristics, nonparametric tests (*Mann-Whitney U test* and *Kruskal Wallis H test*) were performed for independent samples. The results showed that sustainable consumption differs depending on gender. Women tended to report a higher level of resource efficiency behaviour and post-consumption behaviour than men (both $p < 0.05$). Single respondents reported lower SC and WLC than those living with family ($p < 0.05$). Respondents having kids reported lower resource efficiency behaviour ($p < 0.01$) and higher healthy lifestyle behaviour ($p < 0.05$) than respondents without children. There was a significant difference in WLC based on respondents’ position in university: academic staff reported a higher level of work-life conflict than non-academic staff ($p < 0.001$). The results showed significant differences between WLC and SC based on age. Analysis of mean ranks allowed identifying that younger respondents tended to report higher levels of work-life conflict than those, who were 60 years old and above. Meanwhile, the tendency for sustainable consumption behaviour increased for people of 40 years and above.

Conclusions & Discussion

This study represents an attempt to understand the role that work-life balance plays in sustainable consumption behaviour – an issue that was declared as of considerable relevance in SC research field. Since statements about work interferences in private life in relation to sustainable consumption still remain conceptually and empirically underdeveloped, we tried to provide some empirical evidence into the topic.

In general, our study allows confirming that work-life conflict is negatively related to sustainable consumption in private life, but the relationship is rather weak. Analysing SC as five-dimensional construct we found that work-life conflict had a significant negative impact on a healthy lifestyle, which was conceptualized as representing healthy eating and drinking habits. It corresponds to the assumption suggested by Muster that “individuals with high work demands often look for consumption options that require the least work” (Muster, 2012). Our findings allow suggesting that higher levels of WLC do not support a healthy diet and lead to overconsumption or even to possibly heavier alcohol consumption. Work-life conflict does not stimulate more sustainable mobility choices as well. Time-related and/or work-related stress leads to use of less time-consuming travel option (car) when travelling to and from the workplace. Similar results were found when analysing other work-related factors: working hours and working time (working late

Human Factor Analysis in the Labour, Economic and Political Environment

at nights, weekends, etc.) showed a negative association with mobility. Based on the literature we assumed that flexible work schedule should be positively related to sustainable consumption in private life, but the results were opposite (!). We found that work schedule flexibility was negatively related to eco-conscious buying behaviour, healthy lifestyle and overall sustainable consumption. Such nonstandard results might be partly explained by the research context of the present study, as schedule flexibility is common among academic staff in universities. It seems that the flexibility of schedule does not counterbalance the long work hours (at home or at work), heavy work burden and work-related stress. The academic staff has a lot of different roles some of which, e.g., research, does not depend on formal working hours and schedule. On the contrary, the inconsistent schedule may be perceived as a burden to organise daily activities and a healthy lifestyle. Combining with the results that academic staff, who has a flexible schedule, reported a higher level of work-life conflict than non-academic staff (who work conventional hours), those findings can serve as a base for the assumption that schedule flexibility might be seen as professional sector-specific variable. Previous research (Muster, 2011; Muster, 2012; Schultz, Seebacher, 2010) indicated that organisational support for employees' work-life balance efforts is very important for promoting sustainable consumption. Nonetheless, although participants who perceived greater support from their organisations tended to report significantly lower levels of conflict, organisational support did not emerge as having a direct relation with sustainable consumption in private life. In general, our study showed that work hours, work time and organisational support strongly relates to WLC, but do not have a substantial direct impact on sustainable consumer behaviour.

In conclusion, our study showed a possible relation between work-life balance (as opposed to work-life conflict) and sustainable consumption in private life. However further empirical research needs to be conducted on work-related factors determining sustainable consumption because WLB alone is not sufficient.

This study being of exploratory character has a number of limitations. Firstly, the results are limited to the higher education sector. Academic work is essentially unlimited (infinite) and incorporates a wide range of different roles each of which comes with competing demands. Academic profession is known for long work hours, too much administrative paperwork, lack of support, obtaining research funding and finding time for research, frequent interruptions, rapid change, poor salary, lack of promotion prospects, etc. (Kinman, Jones, 2008). Those factors are likely to result in increased perceptions of work-life conflict in the sector. Therefore, the replication of research is needed in other professional settings. Secondly, the results are limited geographically to one small European country Lithuania. Although the academic profession has similar features world-wide, the higher education sector context and sustainable consumption behaviour are subject to variation across different cultural settings. Thirdly, research linking working life and sustainable consumption in private life needs to incorporate other research directions and possible variables (e.g. initiatives of companies to promote sustainable consumption behaviour or employees, two-directional spill-over effects, etc.), because our results show that work-life balance (or work-life conflict) is not sufficient in explaining sustainable consumption behaviour in private life. Finally, further exploration and operationalization of sustainable consumption behaviour is necessary, considering its multidimensional structure. More rigorous testing of the measurement instrument itself is needed. It is well known that measures determine the data, and the latter determines the guidelines for actions. However, we believe that work-life research area can provide some valuable insights for sustainable consumption behaviour promotion.

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Human Factor Analysis in the Labour, Economic and Political Environment

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DARBO IR ASMENINIO GYVENIMO BALANSAS BEI TVARUS VARTOJIMAS: AR EGZISTUOJA RYŠYS?

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SANTRAUKA

Iki šiol atliktų teorinių ir empirinių tyrimų rezultatai rodo, kad tvaraus vartojimo kontekste darbo vietai atitenka svarbus vaidmuo. Remiantis šiais rezultatais keliami hipotezė, kad darbo vietoje įgyta teigiama patirtis bus perkelta ir pritaikyta asmeniniame gyvenime. Kita vertus, darbinis gyvenimas lemia ir nemažai tvaraus vartojimo apribojimų. Jie aktualizuoja darbo ir asmeninio gyvenimo balanso fenomeno reikšmę pažinimo tvaraus vartojimo elgsenoje aktualumą. Atsižvelgus į nevienareikšmius iki šiol atliktų tyrimų rezultatus, šiame straipsnyje keliamas tikslas atskleisti darbo ir asmeninio gyvenimo balanso bei tvaraus vartojimo sąsajas pasitelkus aukštųjų mokyklų darbuotojų atvejį.

Siekiant įgyvendinti tyrimą, straipsnyje aptariamas teoriškai pagrįstas tvaraus vartojimo konstruktas, konceptualizuojamas darbo ir asmeninio gyvenimo balansas bei kiti su darbu susiję veiksniai. Buvo suformuluotos keturios prielaidos, kurios tikrintos nustatant Lietuvos universitetų darbuotojų inties empirinio darbo ir asmeninio gyvenimo balanso bei tvaraus vartojimo sąsajas. Jos interpretuojamos remiantis 439 visiškai užpildytų klausimynų duomenimis. Tyrimo rezultatai leidžia tvirtinti, kad darbo ir asmeninio gyvenimo konfliktas yra neigiamai susijęs su tvirtu vartojimu asmeniniame gyvenime, tačiau ryšys yra gana silpnas. Nustatyta, kad darbo ir asmeninio gyvenimo konfliktas reikšmingai neigiamai veikia tvarų vartojimą per sveiko gyvenimo būdo dimensiją. Rezultatai atskleidžia, kad svarbiausi darbo veiksniai, kurie galėtų padidinti darbo ir asmeninio gyvenimo balansą, yra organizacijos palaikymas, teisingas atlyginimas bei galimybė pačiam planuoti savo veiklas. Jį labiausiai mažina ilgos darbo valandos ir papildomas darbas iki vėlumos bei savaitgaliais. Apibendrinant empirinio tyrimo rezultatus, galima teigti, kad patvirtintas gana silpnas teigiamas darbo ir asmeninio gyvenimo balanso bei tvaraus vartojimo ryšys. Gauti rezultatai skatina ateities tyrimų kryptį ir suteikia pagrindą kitų tyrimų, susijusių su darbu veiksmų reikšmę tvaraus vartojimo kontekste, aktualumui, kadangi vien darbo ir gyvenimo balansas nepaaiškina tiriamo fenomeno.

REIKŠMINIAI ŽODŽIAI: darbo ir asmeninio gyvenimo balansas, tvarus vartojimas, universitetų darbuotojai.